

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING OF SCHOOL NURSES IN CENTRAL LUZON, PHILIPPINES

Arthur G. Sotto, MAN, MAEd

Nurse II

*Tarlac State University
Tarlac, Region III*

Understanding the interplay between socioeconomic status and psychological wellbeing is crucial for grasping how individuals manage various life challenges. This complexity is especially pertinent for school nurses, whose roles demand balancing professional and personal demands. A recent study delves into these factors, focusing on school nurses in Central Luzon, Philippines, under the Department of Education.

The study explored the socioeconomic status and psychological wellbeing of school nurses across 20 divisions in Central Luzon, including Aurora, Bataan, Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, Tarlac, Zambales, and several cities such as Angeles City and San Fernando City. By using a descriptive-correlational method, researchers aimed to assess how these nurses make decisions and cope with the demands of their profession.

The study utilized a survey instrument adapted from the Stanford SPARQ Tools, with responses measured on a five-point Likert scale. The sample comprised 166 nurses from an initial population of 291, selected after gaining permission from the Department of Education's Central Luzon Regional Director and the superintendents of each school division. Data collection involved sending a Google Form to medical directors, who then distributed it to the division nurses. The confidentiality of responses was ensured, and completed questionnaires were carefully retrieved and analyzed.

The results revealed significant insights into the psychological wellbeing of school nurses. The study categorized psychological wellbeing into six areas. Among these, "autonomy" received the highest average rating of 4.19, indicating that nurses felt relatively confident in their ability to make independent decisions. Conversely, "positive relations" scored the lowest, with a grand mean of 3.11, highlighting issues with trust and relationships among peers.

The study underscores the vulnerabilities faced by school nurses, emphasizing the need for improved working conditions and support systems. Enhancing the wellbeing of school nurses is crucial not only for their own health but also for maintaining high-quality healthcare services for students. Addressing the identified issues can help in reducing burnout, improving job satisfaction, and promoting health equity.

Insights from this research are valuable for informing policy development and advocacy efforts. By focusing on the socioeconomic and psychological challenges faced by school nurses, stakeholders can develop strategies to support these essential professionals better. This, in turn, can positively impact the health and wellbeing of both students and the broader community in Central Luzon.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.183-184 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Overall, the study provides a thorough understanding of the factors influencing the psychological wellbeing of school nurses, offering a foundation for future improvements in the field.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13354670

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.